

CHARACTERIZING LARGE-SCALE HYBRID-MANUFACTURED TOOL DURABILITY THROUGH A SMALL-SCALE COMPOSITE PROCESS SCHEME

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Keywords: Hybrid-manufacturing, Tooling, Durability

ABSTRACT

A small-scale composite process scheme was developed to investigate hybrid manufactured tool wear experienced during composite processing using minimal materials and manufacturing to produce test specimens. Evaluation of the surface roughness and morphology through laser profilometry captured considerable variation between the surfaces of each tool both in terms of their as-fabricated state as well as their progressive deterioration with each composite part produced. The surface topology profiles revealed unique wear mechanisms dictated by tool properties resulting from a pseudo wet-layup vacuum bag process, confirming the ability of this process to recreate realistic wear conditions as seen in conventional composite processing methods. Correlating these results with those of the demould testing further revealed that tool performance was not solely dictated by low surface roughness, in some cases higher surface roughness tools surviving more cycles than those of lower surface roughness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Conventional tool design and manufacturing for composite processing is plagued by a combination of material and labour costs when using metal and/or composite materials [1]. Alternatively, Large-Scale Hybrid-Manufacturing (LSHM), a manufacturing technique that synergizes thermoplastic additive and subtractive processes on a single machine, is an emerging technology that can potentially address these issues, reducing labour, time, and material costs through its rapid and semi-autonomous performance [1-3].

Despite the potential of LSHM, its practical implementation is hindered by current research and development test methods, which typically involve full-scale production of the complex tool and its repeated use to assess critical aspects of tool durability [2,4]. Though these tests do give good insight into the tool properties and fabrication process parameters, it comes at substantial material (kgs used), time (long print times), and labour (complex part design and process optimization) costs. There is a need to develop cost-effective test methods that can minimize or eliminate the need for large-scale testing while still determining critical tool properties and manufacturing process parameters.

Small-scale approaches to address this gap in LSHM research are gaining traction but are still in their infancy [5,6]. In this work, a small-scale composite process test scheme is proposed that minimizes large-scale hybrid manufacturing while still obtaining key details regarding tool durability, the results of which can be used for informed future testing and subsequent scale-up for industrial manufacturing.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and Tool Manufacturing

All tool samples consisted of a 25.4 mm x 25.4 mm plate of variable thickness (insignificant for testing) in which one surface was polished and then coated as documented previously [5] (Table 1). Hybrid tools were prepared using a 20 wt% carbon fibre-reinforced acrylonitrile butadiene-co-styrene (CF-ABS) feedstock material in pellet form supplied by the extruder manufacturer. To produce the hybrid tools, a two bead thick (~16 mm) hollow hexagon was first printed and then machined into the

25.4 mm x 25.4 mm plates, of which one side on each (perpendicular to the print direction) was then machined and polished to a 500 grit (0.18 μm) surface finish. These polished tools were then coated with either a naphtha-based sealant (S2) or ceramic-reinforced polymer (C-P), identified to be the most promising non-stick surfaces in previous work [5]. Aluminum (AL) and glass-fibre epoxy (GF-Epoxy) samples coated with another naphtha-based sealant (S1) were provided by industrial partner to serve as an industrial benchmark in addition to one set of glass-fibre epoxy samples that were coated with the ceramic-reinforced polymer. For each tool type, 3 samples were prepared.

Tool Type	Tool Material	Tool Type	Coating
AL (S1)	Aluminum	Traditional (Metal)	Mould Sealant 1
GF-Epoxy (S1)	Glass-Fibre Epoxy	Traditional (Composite)	Mould Sealant 1
GF-Epoxy (C-P)	Glass-Fibre Epoxy	Traditional (Composite)	Ceramic-Polymer
CF-ABS (C-P)	Carbon-Fibre ABS	Hybrid	Ceramic-Polymer
CF-ABS (S2)	Carbon-Fibre ABS	Hybrid	Mould Sealant 2

Table 1: Tool-coating combinations investigated in the small-scale composite processing scheme. ABS: Acrylonitrile butadiene-co-styrene, S1: Sealant 1, C-P: Ceramic-polymer, S2: Sealant 2.

2.2 Small-Scale Composite Process Scheme

The small-scale composite process scheme consisted of laser profilometry, a pseudo wet-layup vacuum bag (WLVB) process, and a demould test to accurately characterize tool surface degradation with each successive use.

Laser profilometry was employed to obtain surface roughness values (R_a [μm]) and morphology details of each tool surface in the as-fabricated state as well as after each composite process. A Zygo NewView Profilometer was used with 2.75x magnification at 1x zoom to capture a 3 mm x 3 mm field of view (FOV) with a lateral resolution of 2.97 mm. For each tool, one scan was performed in the as-fabricated state as well as after each small-scale composite process cycle until the tool was eliminated from the composite trial according to the demould test criteria. For each scan, the region of interest (ROI) was chosen at random and in turn gave the surface profile of the 3 mm x 3 mm region on the tool surface, in addition to the average surface roughness.

The pseudo-WLVB process (Figure 1) was employed to recreate the mechanical and chemical wear conditions a tool would typically experience in-service to produce composite parts. In this process, 25.4 mm x 25.4 mm (L x W) composite parts were repeatedly manufactured on each tool-coating combination until they were eliminated from the test as specified by demould testing. The composite parts consisted of 4 plies of dry biaxial plain weave carbon fibre (~200 gsm) wetted with an epoxy-based liquid resin system mixed 100:12 (Resin:Hardener) by weight according to the manufacturer's guidelines. Composite part configuration was not deemed important for this work as the predominate focus was on the interaction of the tool and part surfaces.

Figure 1: General assembly for the pseudo wet-layup vacuum bag process.

For each cycle, dry plies were first wetted off-tool with an excess of mixed epoxy to ensure complete wetting before being assembled on the tool-coating combinations surface and covered with non-stick composite release film (A4000R, Airtech), breather (Airweave N10, Airtech), and vacuum bag (742601M, Airtech). No mould release agent was used for any processing to accelerate the wear conditions of the tool-coating combinations and, furthermore, eliminate any variability due to additional reagents used during processing (ex. quantity of mould release used, repeatability of application). The entire assembly was then placed in an oven held at 90 °C, covered with two 9.3 kg stone slabs (pre-heated in the oven) to simulate atmospheric pressure, and left to cure for 1 hour.

For demould testing, a 2-stage procedure was employed to track the demould performance of each tool-coating after use. In the first stage, the composite part was attempted to be removed from the tool using varying degrees of effort, ranging from “easy” (hands-only) to “hard” (considerable effort required while using a chisel) as seen in Table 2. If the composite part was successfully removed from the tool, it remained for subsequent small-scale composite processing. However, if this was not possible it was deemed to have “failed”, the tool eliminated from subsequent small-scale tests and assigned a 2-letter demould code to qualitatively characterize the associated failure mode. As the focus of this work was to predominately characterize the performance of hybrid-manufactured tooling, demould testing was continued until all hybrid tool-coating combinations had failed, the last remaining hybrid tool-coating combination representing the most durable hybrid tool.

Stage	Identifier	Description
1	E	Easy to demould composite part. Can be done by hand.
	M	Some effort required to demould composite part. Requires some use of chisel.
	H	Hard to demould composite part. Requires excessive use of chisel.
2	TF	Tool failure. When demoulding part from tool, tool fractures.
	PF	Composite part failure. When demoulding part from tool, any part remains on tool surface.

Table 2: Two-stage demould code used for the characterization of tool demoulding performance and failure.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Laser Profilometry

Profilometry of all tools prior to any composite processing (i.e. in their as-fabricated state) showed that, despite 500 grit (0.18 µm) polishing, all had surface roughness values that varied greatly from the target mould surface finish (Figure 2). Not only this, the variation of surface roughness between each tool-coating combination was significant, with varying degrees of surface homogeneity. As the final

coating and polishing of all tools was performed by the industrial partner, the exact cause for surface roughness variation is unknown. However, it is most likely due to the combined effects of material, manufacturing method, and/or technician skill when polishing and/or coating the tools [7-11].

Figure 2: Surface profiles of as-fabricated tools and their corresponding average surface roughness.

Looking at the surface profiles of all tools with each subsequent cycle, it can be seen that whereas some tools maintained a generally consistent topography, others experienced significant change due to the composite process (Figure 3 – Figure 5). AL (S1), GF-Epoxy (S1), and GF-Epoxy (C-P) looked the same after all cycles (Figure 3), whereas the CF-ABS (S2) and CF-ABS (C-P) tools were significantly affected due to composite processing (Figure 3). CF-ABS (S2) tools clearly showed signs of fibre imprinting after each cycle, with indents that appeared to be transferred from the individual tows of the composite part fabric (Figure 4). This ultimately shows the importance of sufficient tool surface hardness to resist indentation and maintain an as-fabricated surface finish [5-7]. CF-ABS (C-P) showed clear signs of the C-P coating being stripped away from the tool after being demoulded, which would suggest that the bond between the tool and coating was relatively poor compared to the bond between the coating and the composite part (Figure 5) [2,5,6]. This could be clearly seen visually, however, due to the size of the laser profilometry scan, it was possible to miss these signs of tool wear. As such, future work should potentially use a larger scan area to capture the wear of the entire surface after each cycle.

Figure 3: Laser profilometry scans of AL (S1), GF-Epoxy (S1), and GF-Epoxy (C-P) tools at start and after 3 cycles of small-scale composite process testing.

Figure 4: Laser profilometry scans of CF-ABS (S2) over the first 3 cycles showing increasing wear due to fibre imprinting.

Figure 5: Optical image and laser profilometry scan of CF-ABS (C-P) after composite processing, highlighting the ability to miss signs of tool wear.

3.2 Pseudo-WLVB

The pseudo-WLVB process was fairly repeatable, with composite parts of similar quality being produced with each cycle. However, issues arose due to a combination of the method in which pressure was applied as well as tool edge effects. During the application of the stone slabs on top of the entire assembly, if they were not placed carefully, the composite parts would slide off the tools due to a free-floating effect between the tool surface and the composite part resin during initial assembly (Figure 6).

Furthermore, this same effect led to minor shifting of the plies during compaction which resulted in part dimensions greater than 25.4 mm x 25.4 mm. This free-floating effect was mitigated through slight pre-compaction of the plies prior to the application of the weight, ensuring initial consolidation of the plies and removal of any excess resin between the composite part and the tool. However, this additional resin bleed during part compaction was undesirable as after cure, the additional resin along the sides of the tool could potentially lead to additional resistance during demoulding. Though this could potentially be mitigated through decreased resin use, however this runs the risk of under-wetting the dry plies which could, furthermore, potentially decrease wetting of the tool surface [12] which was critical in this work to characterize tool durability. This could potentially be addressed through redesign of the tools such that dams/barriers can be incorporated along the perimeter.

Figure 6: Free-floating edge effect during ply compaction leading to misaligned plies.

3.3 Demould Testing

Results of demould testing indicate that the durability of hybrid manufactured tools tested was limited by the inherent strength of the tool material (Table 3). AL (S1) and GF-Epoxy (S1) tools were relatively easy to demould after all cycles performed, showing no signs of increased resistance to demoulding except for after the 3rd cycle, in which the perceived difficulty had increased for the latter. GF-Epoxy (C-P) tools were difficult to demould for all tests. However, there appeared to be no appreciable signs of failure until after the 3rd cycle, after which 1 of 3 tools experienced composite part failure (Figure 7a). Tools that experienced part failure appeared to be significantly influenced by the edge effect discussed previously, demonstrating the importance of eliminating this in future work through improved sample design. For almost all hybrid manufactured tools the primary failure mode appeared to be tool failure (Figure 7bc), which suggests it was the limiting factor in tool durability. This was potentially exacerbated by the edge effects. Taking a closer look at this failure mode, all hybrid tools appeared to experience tool failure due to interlayer bond failure in the X/Y print direction (i.e. between printed beads). This highlights the importance of optimizing print settings to ensure a robust, repeatable, 3D print with strong interlayer bonding in both the X, Y, and Z directions [13].

Tool Type	Tool Identifier	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3
AL (S1)	AL-S1-1	E	E	E
	AL-S1-2	E	E	E
	AL-S1-3	E	E	E
GF-Epoxy (S1)	GFE-S1-1	<i>E</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>M</i>
	GFE-S1-2	<i>E</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>M</i>
	GFE-S1-3	<i>E</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>M</i>
GF-Epoxy (C-P)	GFE-CP-1	M	H	M
	GFE-CP-2	H	M	M
	GFE-CP-3	M	M	PF
CF-ABS (C-P)	CFABS-CP-1	<i>E</i>	TF	-
	CFABS-CP-2	<i>M</i>	TF	-
	CFABS-CP-3	TF	-	-
CF-ABS (S2)	CFABS-S1-1	E	E	PF
	CFABS-S1-2	E	TF	-
	CFABS-S1-3	E	TF	-

Table 3: Results of demould testing. E: Easy to demold. M: Medium effort to demold. H: Hard to demold. TF: Tool failure. PF: Part failure. Further details regarding each identifier can be found in Table 2.

Figure 7: (a) GF-Epoxy (C-P) composite part failure after 3rd cycle. Tool failure of (b) CF-ABS (S2) and (c) CF-ABS (C-P).

3.4 Holistic Analysis of Small-Scale Composite Process Scheme

The relative performance of each tool can be viewed through the changes in surface roughness, where it was seen that higher surface roughness did not always imply poor performance with respect to durability. Given the fact that all tool types had different as-fabricated surface roughness, to better make a comparison all Ra data was normalized according to the following equation:

$$R_a(\text{Normalized}) = \frac{R_a(i)}{R_a(\text{initial})} - 1, \quad i = \text{cycle} \quad (1)$$

$R_a(\text{Normalized})$: Normalized surface roughness [unitless]

$R_a(i)$: Surface roughness for cycle i [μm]

$R_a(\text{initial})$: Initial surface roughness [μm]

This allowed all tools to start at the same initial value (i.e. 0 at 0 cycles), with subsequent values representing the change in surface roughness of the given tool relative to its initial as-fabricated surface roughness (Figure 8). Both hybrid tools experienced the first significant change in surface roughness, where the predominant reason for this change appeared to be coating removal. CF-ABS (S2) however had the additional impact of fibre imprinting, which is expected to be due to the inherent mechanical properties of sealant 2 not offering any significant hardness to the overall tool. Conversely, the ceramic-polymer coating demonstrated comparatively higher hardness. It is expected that the former issue (i.e. composite part-coating adhesion) could be improved through two distinct pathways: improved coating adhesion to the tool and/or reduced composite part-coating adhesion by using a mould release agent [14,15]. Both would prolong the life of the coatings used. However, the latter issue of fibre imprinting must be addressed by the inherent mechanical properties of the base tool substrate and/or coating [4,6]. As a result of the wear incurred by these tools (and the corresponding increase in Ra), both tool types most likely provided poor surfaces for subsequent cycles, leading to increased adhesion between the tool/coating and composite part as well as their subsequent early failure.

Figure 8: Combined small-scale processing results (a) including and (b) excluding hybrid tool types.

The remaining tools (i.e. AL (S1), GF-Epoxy (S1), and GF-Epoxy (C-P)) showed minimal change in surface roughness, with only one of the GF-Epoxy (C-P) tools experiencing composite part failure. This failure was most likely due to the edge effects previously described, as visual observation of the available tool surface revealed no distinct difference to the tools that had passed, which was confirmed

through laser profilometry. It was interesting to note that even though GF-Epoxy (C-P) tools had the highest initial surface roughness of all fabricated tools, and was difficult to demould after every cycle, it still maintained its initial surface roughness and showed no appreciable signs of coating degradation. This could potentially be explained by the egg carton topography of the tool surface contributing to decreased adhesion [7,11], the effort required to demould composite parts largely dominated by the aforementioned edge effects. The performance of AL (S1) and GF-Epoxy (S1) tools from their initial as-fabricated state is potentially the result of the sealant 1 coating, as despite being vastly different materials, both showed no signs of wear, and remained easy to demould. This would potentially confirm the manufacturer's advertisement of a high-modulus, durable coating with high adhesion to the base tool substrate, which would indirectly resist adhesion with the composite part during processing (i.e. the tool-coating bond is stronger than the coating-composite part adhesion) [2,4,5].

4 CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

With hybrid manufacturing, it is clear that there is an inherent need for low-cost predictive methods to determine the performance of both the additive and subtractive processes and properties of the final tool. Otherwise, due to the plethora of settings for each respective process, significant time is spent iterating to determine the most optimal combination of settings through both. The proposed small-scale composite process scheme gave a low-cost, structured approach to determining tool performance by characterizing incremental tool degradation with each successive composite part produced. Laser profilometry accurately captured degradation of tool surface with repeated use through changes in surface roughness. The wet-layup vacuum bag process successfully exposed the tool surface to physical and chemical wear present in actual composite process. Demould testing after each composite part fabrication was straightforward due to the relatively simple 2-stage assessment criteria and showed that hybrid tool performance was predominately dictated by the mechanical strength of the inter-bead bonding.

Despite the utility of the small-scale composite processing scheme, results of the current procedure employed shows clear avenues of improvement to yield more impactful results. Laser profilometry results revealed the potential for small scan areas to not capture full extent of tool wear was identified, which could be addressed in future work through an increased scan area per tool, or potentially the adoption of an alternate technology that is able to scan the entire tool surface. In the pseudo-WLVB process, the method of simulating vacuum pressure was cumbersome and tools tested had simple topography (i.e. flat plates). Given that this was largely due to the small tool size used (25.4 mm x 25.4 mm), a larger tool geometry could be used in future testing such that an actual vacuum source could be employed. Characterization through demould testing was entirely qualitative where quantitative methods would be more preferable. In future work, incorporation of a quantitative technique to characterize the demould force would greatly compliment the small-scale test method.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by our partners at the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC) and PRIMA Québec. The authors would also like to thank the support of the industrial partner for the assistance in preparing both traditional and hybrid tools.

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